

A SIMPLIFIED FE² MODEL OF FIBRE FAILURE AND ITS CONSEQUENCES APPLIED TO THE DESIGN OF COMPOSITE PRESSURE VESSELS.

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SUMMARY

A multiscale model is presented allowing carbon fibre failures to be related to the instability of composite pressure vessels. Fibre failure controls the ultimate reliability of the vessel and the elastic fibres undergo delayed failure, during the lifetime of the structure, due to the viscoelastic nature of the matrix.

Keywords: Carbon fibre composite pressure vessels, multiscale modelling, life prediction, testing procedures

INTRODUCTION

Advanced composites used for pressure vessels are being increasingly used for onboard applications for vehicles such as buses, utility vehicles and private cars. Composites are ideally suited for this application due to their light weight, high strength and rigidity. They are presently used for storing natural gas at pressures at 20MPa and will be used increasingly to store hydrogen at pressures of 70MPa. The pressure vessels must be tested periodically to ensure their safe continuing use in service. There are no proof testing techniques or in-service reliability assessments techniques which are mentioned in standards that are suitable or based on the failure processes known to control lifetimes of composite structures. The standards which are described are based on the behaviour of metals which fail by crack propagation. These tests subject the pressure vessels to a brief overload, of one and a half times the maximum service pressure, and if the vessel survives it is allowed to continue in service. In this test any incipient crack will be expected to undergo plastic deformation at the crack tip, which at lower loads will impede further crack growth at lower pressures. This mechanism occurs in metals but not in composites for which simple crack propagation and plastic deformation do not dominant failure. An alternative technique of visual inspection is unsuitable for assessing the state of damage of composite materials.

Filament wound composites are made by winding fibres on geodesic paths on a mandrel, which later serves as a liner to ensure gas tightness. This means that when the vessel is pressurised the fibres are subjected only to tensile forces and at the level of the fibres, an analogy can be made with the behaviour of a unidirectional composite loaded in the fibre direction. Failure of the composite requires the fibres to break. In addition the burst strengths of the pressure vessels are controlled by the layer of fibres at 90° to the

major axis. In the case of a unidirectional carbon fibre composite, the fibres support around 99% of the load. Carbon fibre failure is therefore the mechanism which determines the failure of the composite pressure vessel, not crack propagation as is assumed in standards.

The consequences of fibre failure in composite materials have been examined in a number of studies beginning with Cox who developed a 2-D analytical analysis of load sharing between elastic fibres embedded in an elastic matrix [1]. This study revealed the fundamental mechanism controlling composite behaviour to be load transfer from the matrix, which undergoes shear near the fibre, to which it is well bonded, to the fibre which experiences tensile loads which increase from its end. By writing equations of equilibrium between the shear forces in the matrix and the tensile forces in the fibre, Cox was able to provide analytical solutions for the stress states in and around short fibres in a matrix. Subsequent studies considered perfectly plastic matrices and were shown to simplify the analysis [2]. Other studies considered the effects of fibre failure on the other unbroken fibres in a composite [3, 4]. It was shown that the effect of a fibre break in composite was confined to a small volume of material around the break and that only the fibres immediately neighbouring the fibre break experienced any change of stress. With the availability of computers and increasing computational capacity this situation has been the subject of many subsequent two and three dimensional numerical studies, including a few which consider that the effects of a viscoelastic matrix [5- 7].

Studies in our group have examined this problem with the aim of improving the models and applying the results to various filament wound structures, including pressure vessels. In order to tackle this problem an immediate practical problem has to be considered. In a unidirectional cfrp specimen with a cross section of 20mm x 1mm there are about 136,000 fibres. In any cross section of a CNG tank there are around 125 million fibres. It is clear that any attempt to model the behaviour of a complete structure with a discretisation at the level of the individual fibres would encounter unacceptable computational times. The FE² multi-scale approach which has been adopted to overcome these difficulties can be seen to share points in common described in references [8 and 9].

DESCRIPTION OF THE MICROSCOPIC FAILURE PROCESS

In this study, both the fibres and the matrix are considered to be homogeneous continua. The orthorhombic spatial frame used at the microscopic level is $R_{loc} = (O, \bar{x}, \bar{y}, \bar{z})$ for which (x, y, z) describe the coordinates of a point M . The vector \bar{z} is aligned parallel to the fibres. Earlier studies have allowed the Representative Volume Element (RVE) to be defined for the undamaged composite [10-15]. If the composite is considered to be periodic with a hexagonal fibre arrangement in the (\bar{x}, \bar{y}) plane, the periodic cell which is representative of the RVE, called CS32, consists of 32 fibres. Its geometry is a parallelepiped with the \bar{z} axis parallel to the fibres with a square section with sides of length c (Fig.1). The length in the \bar{z} direction was taken to be between the planes $z = 0$ and $z = L = 8\text{mm}$ [13]. The reference origin O is the geometrical centre of the section in the plane $z = 0$. At this scale, at point M , the stress and strain tensors are σ and ε .

Earlier studies have shown that this approach accurately describes what happens in the vicinity of a fibre break [10-12] and can account for : the random nature of fibre breaks and the points of failure along the fibres; the number of breaks in a RVE at five levels of damage from the undamaged to the failed state (these states are : C32,C16, C8, C4, C2 (Fig. 1) containing respectively 1, 2, 4, 8, 16 broken fibres amongst the 32 present in the CS32 cell) ; the load transfer to and along the intact fibres due to the fibre failures; the effects of interfacial debonding, around fibre breaks on load transfer to intact fibres (ten debonding lengths have been considered from 3.5 to 35 μm in steps of 3.5 μm); the effects of the viscoelastic nature of the matrix (taken as linear) on load transfer to neighbouring intact fibres; the present study also takes into account the fibre volume fraction.

The coefficient of load transfer along the lengths of the fibres is given by:

$$k_r(C, d, t, V_f, Z) = \frac{\int_{Z_i}^{Z_{i+1}} \int_{S_F} \sigma_{zz}(C, d, t, V_f, x, y, z) dx dy dz}{\int_{Z_i}^{Z_{i+1}} \int_{S_F} \sigma_{zz}(CS32, d=0, t=0, V_f, x, y, z) dx dy dz}$$

In which; C is the cell representing the state of damage considered; d is the debonded length; t is the time after fibre failure; V_f is the fibre volume fraction, z is the coordinate along the fibre from the plane of failure (z=0), Z_{i+1} and Z_i are the abscissa of the plane sections between which k_r is calculated

$$Z = \frac{Z_{i+1} + Z_i}{2}$$

S_F indicates the cross section of the fibre considered, x, y are the coordinates of the plane section of the cell; σ_{zz} is the axial stress in the fibre considered.

Whether or not there is debonding at the fibre/matrix interface or if the matrix is viscoelastic, or not, the definition for k_r remains valid.

Construction of a data base at the microscopic scale

If one cell is considered and a debond length of 140 μm taken, the calculation time to obtain geometrical convergence for a periodic homogenisation requires approximately a discretisation for 250,000 nodes and two hours of calculation time for an all elastic model. If this approach is applied to a macroscopic structure, for which the number of Gauss points is in the thousands, the calculation time would be unacceptably long. A less time consuming approach is therefore necessary.

The load transfer function has been smoothed, assuming a linear function, and only the load transfer in the fibre nearest to the fibre break calculated. In order to separate the effects of interfacial debonding and those due to the viscoelastic shear of the matrix, we put $k_r = K_r + K_r^d + K_r^v$ in which; K_r is the part of the load transfer exclusively due to the failure of the fibre; K_r^d is due to the debond with K_r^d = 0, if this is not considered; K_r^v is due exclusively to the viscoelastic behaviour of the matrix with K_r^v = 0 if viscoelasticity is not considered.

These smoothed parameters are used as a data base describing the microscopic scale considered in the multiscale FE² model. Using the overall stress applied on the macroscopic scale, the duration of the load and the state of damage, this data base allows, by linearity, to know the longitudinal stress state in the fibres at the microscopic scale, without resolving the problem at the microscopic scale by the finite element method and the evolution of the damage, consisting of increasing numbers of fibre breaks in the RVE can be evaluated. It is assumed that the failure of a fibre induces a debond length of 35µm which has been shown to result in the greatest stress concentration in neighbouring intact fibres.

In order to compare the relative influences of different physical phenomena, for different fibre volume fractions, six levels of refinement in the model have been considered : the first taking into account only fibre breaks; the second adds the effect of load transfer, through the matrix on intact fibres neighbouring the fibre break; the third includes the effects of fibre matrix debonding from the point of failure and then the previous three degrees of sophistication are again considered but the viscoelastic nature of the matrix is included.

Description of the macroscopic scale justifying the use of parallel computation

The carbon fibres had radii of 3.5µm so that the dimensions of three CS32 cells, representing three fibre volume fractions of 19%, 39% and 64%, were respectively 0.080mm x 0.080mm x 8mm, 0.056mm x 0.056mm x 8mm and 0.044mm x 0.044mm x 8mm. Their volumes were $V_{19\%}=0.0512\text{mm}^3$, $V_{39\%}=0.0251\text{mm}^3$, $V_{64\%}=0.0155\text{mm}^3$. Calculations for plate specimens have shown that the mesh necessary for convergence can be carried out with finite elements (of the c3d8 type) containing 4 RVEs.

If the cylindrical part of the pressure vessel is 500mm long, with an internal radius of 100mm and a composite wall thickness of 10mm, assuming a fibre volume fraction of 39%, the finite element mesh would consist of 40 million elements each consisting of four RVEs and as many nodes. This would result in 300 million Gauss points and 120 million of degrees of freedom. A pure FE² calculation would involve 300 million x 2 = 600 million hours of calculation time. Parallel computing becomes indispensable. To reduce the calculation time at the macroscopic scale certain assumptions have been made to further simplify the problem when considering the long-term macroscopic behaviour of a unidirectional composite. These hypotheses are based on experimental results and do not affect the quality of the final result.

At the macroscopic scale, the composite can be seen as an equivalent homogeneous material, which can be described within orthorhombic coordinates, $b_{loc} = (\vec{x}_1, \vec{x}_2, \vec{x}_3)$.

The \vec{x}_1 vector is aligned parallel to the fibre direction. At this scale at the point M , the stress tensor is Σ and the strain tensor is E .

The first hypothesis is that the fibre failures are the mechanism necessary for the failure of the structure. Other failure processes are not considered. Secondly it is assumed that, unlike the microscopic behaviour, viscoelastic effects of the matrix, on the macroscopic scale, are negligible. The nonlinear behaviour of the homogenised material is considered only to be due to fibre failure and reflects the density of broken fibres.

The variation of the elastic modulus of the equivalent homogeneous material as a function of the density of fibre breaks could be solved as a problem of periodic homogenisation. However, an approximation, based on the law of mixtures, which gives an upper bound, gives an acceptable result. Finally, at the macroscopic scale and in the b_{loc} base, the behaviour of the unidirectional composite is given by $\sum(\mathbf{M}) = \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{M}) : \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{M})$ with $\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{M}) = \mathbf{a}^0(\mathbf{M})$, where $\mathbf{a}^0(\mathbf{M})$ describes the rigidity tensor of the undamaged material at the point M , except $\mathbf{a}_{1111}(\mathbf{M}) = \mathbf{a}_{1111}^0 \left\{ 1 - \frac{N_R(\mathbf{M})}{N_T} \right\}$ in which N_R, N_T (32 in our case) are respectively the number of broken fibres and the total number of fibres in the RVE. From the second assumption it can be seen that it is only the increase in load in intact fibres neighbouring a fibre break at the microscopic level which is important in determining behaviour. This hypothesis justifies only the increase in loading parallel to the fibre axis being considered.

Multiscale calculation

Input data for this calculation are: at the macroscopic scale: the characteristics of the undamaged composite and the law describing the fall in longitudinal rigidity of the equivalent homogenous material; at the microscopic scale, for each Gauss point: the random choice of 5 failure stresses according to Weibull statistics, describing the stochastic fibre failure strengths; the data base allowing the axial stresses supported by the fibres in the RVE to be known and the evolution of the damage from the undamaged state in CS32 to complete failure represented by C2.

The multiscale simplified FE² calculation is iterative and calculates the state of damage (number of fibres broken), at iterative step n , having determined the state of damage at step $n-1$ in the following manner: a time increment is considered together with or without a change to the macroscopic stress depending on whether an increase in load is made or whether the test is at constant load; the finite element calculation at the macroscopic scale determines the macroscopic stress on the composite in the direction of the fibres: reiteration at the Gauss points for the microscopic scale: A localisation step relates the macroscopic stress and the damage state of the material, the data base for load transfer is applied to calculate the axial stress in the fibres in the RVEs. This stress allows the number of broken fibres in the RVE to develop by comparison with the failure stresses selected from the Weibull analysis. A homogenisation step is then used to calculate the macroscopic behaviour of the homogenised equivalent material taking into account the new state of damage. The next incremental step in the iteration process as a function of time can then be calculated.

The case of unidirectional plate specimens

The approach described above to model damage accumulation has been used to predict the failure of unidirectional plate specimens loaded in the fibre direction. The model accurately predicts tensile failure to within $\pm 2\%$ and that by increasing the complexity of the model to include fibre-matrix debonding the scatter of composite properties can be simulated (12). The same reference examines the effects of the viscoelastic properties of the matrix on the long term behaviour of the composite. It is shown that the model is capable of predicting the scatter of rates fibre failures when compared to

experimental curves obtained by acoustic emission. The present study has taken into account the variation of Weibull modulus which occurs when selecting just thirty two fibres from a large fibre population. Although the large population will have a characteristic value of Weibull modulus, the random choice of thirty two fibres will lead to a wide distribution of the value [14]. The results of including the range of possible values of the Weibull modul can be seen in Figure 1, which shows damage accumulation under a steady load. These results confirm that damage increases with time and that the spread of the increase of damage when different specimens are subjected to the same applied load is increased over and above that obtained due to the scatter in fibre strengths because of the effects of considering a limited number of fibres in the RVE.

Figure 1: Simulated fibre failures in unidirectional composites held at a constant load of 80% of failure load showing scatter due to the stochastic nature of fibre strengths and also variations in Weibull moduli between the A and B curves.

When these results are compared to experimentally obtained curves, as shown in Figure 2, there is very good agreement.

Application to the behaviour of a composite pressure vessel

Figure 3 shows simulations of burst tests on pressure vessels of various fibre volume fractions. Although the lower values of V_f considered are unlikely to be found in real structures, the less than regular distribution of the fibres could lead to such values being found at certain points in the structure.

Figure 2: Comparison of simulated and experimental results of constant load tests, at 80% failure stress, with unidirectional specimens loaded in the fibre direction.

Figure 3: Simulated burst tests for three pressure vessels with various fibre volume fractions.

The points at which the curves begin to deviate significantly from linearity are taken to show when fibre breaks begin to interact and result in a physical instability of the pressure vessel.

Figure 4 shows a simulation of the accumulation of fibre breaks in a pressure vessel, designed to have a burst pressure of approximately 80 MPa, when it is held at 50MPa. The crosses represent the calculated values and the continuous line the curve fitted to these points. The result reflects the experimental curves obtained experimentally on pressure vessels and published elsewhere [12].

Figure 4: Simulated fibre failures in a pressure vessel maintained at a constant pressure of 50MPa.

Figure 5 shows that the damage accumulated in the composite pressure vessels increases with time, however, this damage consists of regions of fibre breaks isolated by the effect of load transfer through the matrix. A physical instability arises when the density of fibre breaks reaches critical threshold and the regions of damage begin to interfere. The point of physical instability is shown by the point of inflexion in the curve of damage accumulation for the simulated pressure vessel subjected to 60 MPa (600 bars). Although this point does not represent the burst of the pressure vessel it does represent a limit for its reliable use.

The inflexion point, representing the limit of reliability, occurs after increasingly long periods of loading as the applied pressure is reduced and so are not shown for lower pressures.

Figure 5: Fibre breaks occurring in a pressure vessel during pressurisation and then during the maintenance of the pressure constant. The curve for a pressure of 50 MPa (500 bars) shown in the previous figure is reduced because of the reduction in scale. The point of inflection seen on the curve for 70 MPa (700 bars) reveals the point at which regions of damage begin to interact and the pressure vessel is no longer reliable.

CONCLUSION

The accumulation of fibre breaks in unidirectional composites, loaded in the fibre direction has been accurately modelled. A simplified multiscale finite element approach has been employed in which the RVE takes into account the stochastic characteristics of fibre breaks, the variation of Weibull moduli due to finite numbers of fibres being considered, the load transfer through the matrix and its viscoelastic behaviour, as well as interfacial debonding. It has been shown that this model accurately describes the experimental results obtained in monotonic tensile tests and also in steady load tests. The model allows the scatter to be expected in experimental tests to be determined.

The use of parallel computation has allowed the behaviour of whole of the pressure vessels to be modelled. The analogy between the behaviour of unidirectional composites and that of the reinforcements in the pressure vessels has been justified by a comparison between experimental and theoretical results. It has been shown that when the damage density is such that random fibre breaks are no longer isolated in the matrix but that an interaction begins to occur between damaged regions, the rate of damage begins to accelerate. This represents a point of physical instability which determines the limit of the safe use of a pressure vessel.

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